

Hydro-Chemical Assessment of Surface Water Quality for Domestic and Agricultural Uses in Nrobo and Environs, Southeastern, Nigeria

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This study was conducted to assess the hydro chemical properties of surface waters in Nrobo and its suitability for irrigation purposes. Five surface water samples were collected from 5 different spring waters of the area. Some physicochemical parameters were analyzed using standard procedures, and the results were compared with World Health Organization standard limit. However, the concentrations of all the physicochemical parameters are within the standard limits of World Health Organization except pH in few locations whose concentrations are not in line with the standard limit. The type of water that predominates in the study area was of sodium-bicarbonate and sodium-calcium bicarbonate based on hydro-chemical facies. Based on chemical analysis, the samples were classified as per different standard irrigation criteria to study the chemical changes resulting due to rain and natural recharge.

ABSTRACT

Keywords: Hydro-Chemical Assessment; Surface Water Quality; Chemical Classification; Agricultural Uses

Introduction

Water quality is among the most vital areas in hydrogeological studies. Identification of physio-chemical attributes of water is necessary for evaluating the eligibility of water for several needs including drinking, domestic, industrial and irrigation. Water quality may also change with time and seasons. Since, it is basically regulated by the degree and concentration of dissolved solids. Water quality is affected by geogenic and human mediated activities including weather conditions, underlying lithology and irrigation practices. Several approaches and method have been initiated scholars to elucidate the chemical data.

Zaporozee (1972) has introduced different methods of data presentation and has discussed their likely usage. Exhibition of chemical analysis in visual form makes interpretation of complicated surface water system easier and faster. Procedures of describing the chemistry of water like Collin's bar chart, radiating vectors of Maucha (1940), and parallel and horizontal axes of Stiff (1940), have been utilized in several parts of the world to demonstrate the proportion of ionic concentration in specific samples.

Subramanian (1994) followed a set of approach to elucidate and categorize the chemistry of groundwater in basement rock, along with coastal areas in the southern portions of India. In the study area, there is no existing study prior to this topic, hence, the aim of the present study is to characterize the hydro-chemical properties of surface waters in Nrobo and environs.

Study Area

Nrobo is situated in the northeastern part of Uzo-uwani LGA of Enugu state between North latitudes 6°48'0" and 6°53'0" and East longitudes 7°14'0" and 7°19'0" occupying an area extent of 181 sq.km. The area encompasses Ajayigo, Owa, Okpala, Ofum, Umuiya, Umuoyo, Umuamuna, Umuduesua, Ugor, Abi and Ugbene Ajima. The district is among the most densely populated area of the LGA. The total population of the area is about 12,183. The area is characterized by vast conical hills with elevation varying from 125 to 400 m above sea level. Nrobo is drained by several spring waters that emanating from the foot of the hills. These springs include Akpara, Abamti Ogoro, Isiadikor, Adanaogwu, Ufubo and Ide sprins. As described by Igbozulike (1975), the study area falls within the humid rainforest region of southeastern Nigeria with annual rainfall between 1750 and 2500 mm per annum. The area is also characterized by a tropical climate with rainy and seasons. The rainy season spans from April.

Several researchers have looked into the geology of the study area in distinct manners (Reyment 1965; Nwajide 1990; Nwajide 2013). The AJali (Maarstrictian) and Nsukka Formations (Danian) are the principal geological formations underlying the study area. These formations consisting of unconsolidated cross bedded reddish white sand intercalated with siltstone, dark grey colored fissile shale, reddish brown claystone interbedded with ferruginized ironstone.

Materials and Method

Surface water samples were collected from 5 existing spring water located in different sections of the study area during June 2021. The obtained water samples were transferred into precleaned polythene container for analysis of chemical parameters. Chemical analyses were conducted following the standard methods (APHA-2002). Individual samples were measured for pH, electrical conductivity (EC), major cations and major anions. Among the various parameters, pH and EC were analyzed in-situ using portable meters (portable Hannah, pH meter). Calcium and magnesium were measured by ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid titrimetric procedure. Bicarbonate and chloride were analyzed using titrimetric technique. Sodium and potassium were measured using flame photometer. Sulphate was analyzed by gravimetric procedure. Total dissolved solids, RSC, % Sodium, SAR were calculated by estimation. In current research, Piper, Back and Hanshaw, Wilcox, Eaton, Todd and USSL (US Salinity Laboratory) classification were adopted to categorize the hydro chemical properties of surface water of Nrobo and environs.

Piper Diagram

The Piper-Hill Graphics (1953) is employed to presume hydro-geochemical facies. These diagrams include two triangles, one for plotting cations and the other for plotting anions (Figure 1). The cations and anion fields are

integrated to present a single point in a diamond-shaped field, from which assumption is drawn on the basis of hydro-geochemical facies theory. These tri-linear plots are helpful in analyzing chemical associations between surface water samples in more clear terms than with other possible plotting techniques. Chemical data of representative samples from the area is plotted on a Piper-trilinear plot (Figure 2). This diagram indicates the affinities, differences and distinct water type in the study area. The theory of hydro chemical facies was initiated to comprehend and ascertain the water constituents in various group.

Facies are observable parts of various characters affiliated to every naturally connected system. Hydro chemical facies are different parts that bears cation and anion concentration groups. To delineate composition group, Back, W. & Hanshaw, B.B., (1965) recommended subdivisions of the tri-linear plot (Figure 1). The explanation of each facies from the 0 to 10% and 90 to 100% domains on the diamond shaped cation to anion plot is more useful than employing equal 25% accretions. It explains the differences or supremacy of cation and anion concentrations.

Figure 1: Classification diagram for anion and cation facies in the form of major-ion percentages (Piper, 1953).

Wilcox (1995) used percent sodium and electrical conductivity to classify groundwater for irrigation uses. Eaton (1950) advocated measuring the residual sodium carbonate concentration in water to evaluate its appropriateness for irrigation. The US Department of Agriculture's Salinity Laboratory implemented various procedures to describe the appropriateness of water for agricultural purposes. The sodium content of irrigation waters is commonly expressed as a percentage and can be calculated using the equation below.

$$\% \text{ Na} = (\text{Na}^+) \times 100 / (\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+} + \text{Na}^+ + \text{K}^+) \quad (1)$$

Where the amounts of Ca^{2+} , Mg^{2+} , Na^+ , and K^+ are demonstrated in milliequivalents per litre (meq/l). As the water in the soil becomes more concentrated, calcium and magnesium tend to precipitate in waters with high bicarbonate concentrations. As a result, the amount of sodium in the water in the form of sodium carbonate increases. The following equation is used to compute RSC.

$$\text{RSC} = (\text{HCO}_3^- + \text{CO}_3^{2-}) - (\text{Ca}^{2+} + \text{Mg}^{2+}) \quad (2)$$

Where all ionic concentrations are expressed in equivalent per mole.

Water with more than 2.5 epm of RSC is not acceptable for irrigation, according to the US Department of Agriculture. The most vital properties of irrigation water in defining its quality are: i) Total content of soluble salts; ii) Relative proportion of sodium to other major cations; (iii) Content of boron or other parameters that may be harmful, and (iv) Under some condition, bicarbonate level as regards to the content of calcium and magnesium. The salinity hazard, salt hazard, boron hazard, and bicarbonate hazard have all been identified. Previously, the sodium hazard was calculated as a percentage of total cations. The SAR, which is used to quantify responses with the soil, is a better indicator of the sodium threat for irrigation.

SAR is estimated as

$$SAR = \frac{Na^+}{\left(\frac{Ca^{2+}+Mg^{2+}}{2}\right)^{\frac{1}{2}}} \quad (3)$$

Where all ionic concentrations are expressed in equivalent per mole.

The total concentration of dissolved salts (salinity danger) in irrigation water can be described in terms of specific conductance for diagnosis and categorization purposes

Results and Discussion

The water quality parameters (pH, EC, DO, TDS, Ca, Mg, Na, K, Cl, HCO₃, SO₄, NO₃, and PO₄) in the water samples from the Nrobo and environs are listed in Table 1.

Surface water pH ranges from 4.3 to 6.8. This reveals that surface water in the area is predominantly acidic in composition. The EC ranged from 121 to 168 with highest value documented in Abamti Ogoro spring (SP 5). The DO ranged from 28.02 (Abamti Ogoro Spring) to 40.0 mg/L (Isiadikor spring). Water TDS exhibited small variations, varying from 011 (Ufubo spring) to 094 (Abamti Ogoro spring). Cations and anions were relatively very low in surface water samples from the study area. For cations, calcium ranges from 5.0 in Ejuowa spring to 12.52 mg/L in Ide spring while magnesium ranges from 0.56 to 2.63 mg/L. Sodium and potassium ranged from 10.06 in Ejuowa and Abamti Ogoro springs to 20.05 mg/L in Ufubo spring and 5.03 mg/L in Isiadikor spring to 11.07 mg/L in Ufubo spring. For anions, chloride and bicarbonate has concentrations, ranging from 2.01 to 12.13 mg/L and 10.04 to 20.02 mg/L, whereas, sulphate varied from 0.01 mg/L in Ufubo and Abamti Ogoro springs to 0.04 mg/L in Isiadikor spring. Consequently, nitrate had concentration, ranging from 3.0 to 15.0 mg/L. Phosphate has values varying from 1.57 to 3.04 mg/L. A comparison of our results with WHO (2011) drinking water standards for surface water is presented in Table 1. pH in the Ufubo and Ide springs is lower than WHO standard limit, respectively, indicating water pollution with respect to pH.

Table 1: Result of Physio-chemical Parameters of the Analyzed Surface Water Samples

Parameters	Ejuowa Spring (SP1)	Isiadikor Spring (SP2)	Ufubo Spring (SP3)	Ide Spring (SP4)	Abamti Ogoro Spring (SP5)	WHO (2011)
pH	6.7	6.8	4.6	4.7	4.3	6.5 – 8.5
EC	135	138	121	127	168	500
DO	39.08	40.0	39.07	36.04	28.02	
TDS	014	018	011	016	094	500
Ca ²⁺	5.0	7.51	12.48	12.52	12.50	75
Mg ²⁺	1.49	0.56	1.37	2.63	1.66	
Na ⁺	10.06	18.05	20.05	15.10	10.06	250
K ⁺	8.09	5.03	11.07	10.09	7.07	
Cl ⁻	2.01	5.30	8.17	12.13	9.22	250
HCO ₃ ⁻	11.0	15.0	10.04	20.02	18.11	
SO ₄ ²⁻	0.03	0.04	0.01	0.02	0.01	
NO ₃ ⁻	3.0	15.0	10.0	9.0	5.0	45
PO ₄ ²⁻	2.21	3.04	1.94	1.75	1.57	

Hydro-chemical Facie

Piper diagrams are an illustration of water quality charts, and they are arguably the most commonly used nowadays. The divisions of the trilinear or piper diagram show that the area was characterized by Na-Ca and Na-Ca-HCO₃ type water. The percentage of samples falling under Na-Ca and Na-Ca-HCO₃ type of water was (80 %) and 20% in (Table 2). For anion concentration, HCO₃-type of water was predominated with 55% samples while Na with 45% dominate the cations. The appreciable change in the hydro-chemical facies was noticed during the study period, which was might be due to the leaching of alkali salts through precipitation.

Table 2: Characterization of Surface Water of Nrobo and Environs on the Basis of Piper Tri-Linear Diagram

Subdivision of the diamond	Characteristics of corresponding subdivisions of diamond-shaped fields	Percentage of samples in the study area
1	Alkaline earth (Ca+Mg) Exceed alkalies (Na+K)	-
2	Alaklies exceeds alkaline earths	-
3	Weak acids (CO ₂ +HCO ₃) exceed Strong acids (SO ₄ +Cl)	-
4	Strong acids exceed weak acids	-
5	Magnesium bicarbonate type	-
6	Calcium-chloride Type	-
7	Sodium-chloride Type	-
8	Sodium-Bicarbonate Type	80
9	Sodium-calcium-Bicarbonate type	20
10	Calcium-magnesium-Chloride Type	-

Figure 2: Surface Water Samples Plotted in Piper-Trilinear diagram

The classification of surface water samples with respect to per cent sodium is shown in Table 3. It is observed that about 80% of samples fall under permissible to excellent category while 20% samples fall under good category.

Table 3: Sodium Percent Water Class

<i>Sodium (%)</i>	<i>Water class</i>	<i>Samples</i>
<20	Excellent	4.86-10.03 (4 samples)
20-40	Good	20.01 (1 sample)
40-60	Permissible	
60-80	Doubtful	
>80	Unsuitable	

Surface water of the study area is classified on the basis of RSC and the results are presented in Table 4. Based on RSC values, water can be classified as good quality (<1.25 epm) for irrigation use.

Table 4: Surface Water Quality Based on RSC

<i>1. RSC (epm)</i>	<i>2. Remark on Quality</i>	<i>3. Samples</i>
4. <1.25	5. Good	6. 0.36-0.54 (5 samples)
7. 1.25-2.5	8. Doubtful	9. -
10. >2.5	11. Unsuitable	12. -

The classification of surface water samples from the study area with respect to SAR is represented in Table 5. The SAR value of about 80% and 20% of the samples are classified as excellent to good for irrigation. In order to characterize water for irrigation the value of SAR and specific conductance were plotted on the US salinity (USSL) diagram (Figure 3). About 80% and 20% post-monsoon samples are grouped within C1S1 and C1S2 classes (Figure 3).

Table 5: Sodium Hazard Classes Based on USSL Classification

<i>Sodium Hazard class</i>	<i>SAR in Equivalents per mole</i>	<i>Remark on quality</i>	<i>Samples</i>
S1	10	Excellent	2.1-4.3 (4 samples)
S2	10-18	Good	10.8 (1 sample)
S3	18-26	Doubtful	-
S4 and S5	>26	Unsuitable	-

Classification of groundwater based on salinity hazard is presented in Table 6. EC value indicates that about 100% samples were excellent for irrigation purposes.

Table 6: Salinity Hazard Classes

<i>Salinity hazard class</i>	<i>EC in micromohs/cm)</i>	<i>Remark on quality</i>	<i>Samples</i>
C1	100-250	Excellent	23.4-41.8 (5 samples)
C2	250-750	Good	-
C3	750-2,250	Doubtful	-
C4 and C5	>2,250	Unsuitable	-

Figure 3: USSS classification of surface water of the study area

Conclusion

Hydro chemical evaluation of groundwater indicates that Na-HCO₃ and Na-Ca-HCO₃ type water dominates the study area. Na-HCO₃ waters shows high sodality with high soluble sodium percentage and residual sodium carbonate. The rain improved the water quality in terms of RSC and percent sodium as reflected by the reduction in number of unsuitable samples from 67 to 39 % (RSC > 2.5) and from 8 to 5 % (% Sodium > 80). High Bicarbonate is observed in most of the samples which is believed to be due to the recharge from normal groundwater (Ca-HCO₃).

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